

On some Dinitropolyhalogen Derivatives of Benzene.

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It has been shown in earlier papers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 128, 2481; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 299; 1932, 9, 59) that the action of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride on dinitrophenols first observed by Ullmann and Nadai (*Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1870) provides one of the best and readiest methods of replacing a hydroxyl group by a chlorine atom, and if suitable derivatives of benzene containing a hydroxyl group are selected, chloroderivatives of these compounds are obtained containing the chlorine atom in a known position. The chlorine atom so introduced is very labile and is capable of being replaced by various groups. A large number of these chloro derivatives have already been described (*loc. cit.*) and it is proposed in this paper to further characterise them by describing a certain number of derivatives obtained from each.

It is well known that a chlorine atom having two nitro groups in the 2:4 or 2:6 position is very reactive. The reactivity of the halogen atoms in the following four compounds has been studied: 1-chloro-4-bromo-2:6-dinitrobenzene, 1-chloro-4-iodo-2:6 dinitrobenzene, 1-chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrobenzene, 1-chloro-2-iodo-4:6-dinitrobenzene. It has been found that the chlorine atom in each of the above compounds can be directly replaced by the following groups:

These compounds readily react with *p*-phenylenediamine giving rise to diphenyl-*p*-phenylenediamine derivatives. They readily condense with phenylhydrazine forming triazoles. They also react with *o*-aminophenol, a phenoxazine being the product of the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Derivatives from 1-Chloro-4-bromo-2:6-dinitrobenzene.

4-Bromo-2:6-dinitroaniline was obtained by passing a current of ammonia into a boiling alcoholic solution of 1-chloro-4-bromo-2:6-dinitrobenzene (2.8 g.). The liquid soon became reddish; after half an hour the current of ammonia was stopped and the liquid cooled and filtered and the bromodinitroaniline crystallised from alcohol in orange needles, m.p. 159° (cf. Meldola and Streatfield, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1898, 73, 688; see also *Ber.*, 1876, 9, 919). (Found: N, 16.01. Calc.: N, 16.04 per cent).

4-Bromo-2:6-dinitrodiphenylamine.—A solution of 1-chloro-4-bromo-2:6-dinitrobenzene (2.8 g.) in alcohol was heated on the water bath with aniline (2 c.c.). The liquid soon turned red and on cooling the diphenylamine derivative separated out after half an hour and was crystallised from alcohol in orange needles, m.p. 122°, yield 3 g. (Austen, *Ber.*, 1876, 9, 920). (Found: N, 12.15. Calc.: N, 12.43 per cent).

4-Bromo-2:6-dinitrodimethylaniline.—To an alcoholic solution of 1-chloro-4-bromo-2:6-dinitrobenzene (2.8 g.) dimethylamine (33%, 4 c.c.) was added and the mixture boiled on the water-bath for half an hour. On cooling orange-yellow plates separated out (2.3 g.) which were recrystallised from alcohol or from a mixture of acetone and water, m.p. 119°. (Found: N, 14.58. $C_8H_8O_4N_3Br$ requires N, 14.48 per cent).

4-Bromo-2:6-dinitrodiphenylpiperidine.—Piperidine (2 c.c.) was added to a solution of 1-chloro-4-bromo-2:6-dinitrobenzene (2.8 g.) in alcohol and the mixture kept on the boiling water-bath for half an hour; an orange compound separated out on adding some water and cooling; orange yellow needles from dilute alcohol and also from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 110°, yield 2.9 g. (Found: N, 12.46. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4N_3Br$ requires N, 12.73 per cent).

Dibromotetranitrodiphenyl-p-phenylenediamine.—A solution of 1-chloro-4-bromo-2:6-dinitrobenzene (2.8 g.) in alcohol, *p*-phenylenediamine (0.6 g.) and anhydrous sodium acetate (3 g.) were heated on a boiling water-bath. The liquid soon darkened and dark crystals began to separate. After about 45 minutes the liquid was cooled and filtered. The *p*-phenylenediamine derivative dissolves sparingly in alcohol and acetone and moderately in acetic acid and crystallises

from an excess of acetic acid in dark red crystals, m.p. above 300°, yield 2.6 g. (Found: N, 13.79. $C_{18}H_{10}O_8N_6Br_2$ requires N, 14.05 per cent).

3-Bromo-5-nitrophenoxazine.—1-Chloro-4-bromo-2:6-dinitrobenzene (2.8 g.) dissolved in alcohol, *o*-aminophenol (1.2 g.) and anhydrous sodium acetate (3 g.) were heated on a boiling water-bath. The liquid soon became dark and crystals began to separate. After about an hour the liquid was cooled and filtered. The phenoxazine dissolves sparingly in alcohol and moderately in acetic acid and crystallises from acetic acid in violet silky needles, m.p. 179°, yield 1.4 g. (Found: N, 8.83; Br, 26.0. $C_{12}H_7O_3N_2Br$ requires N, 9.12; Br, 26.04 per cent).

2-Phenyl-5-bromo-7-nitropseudoaziminobenzene.—A solution of 1-chloro-4-bromo-2:6-dinitrobenzene (2.8 g.) in alcohol and phenylhydrazine (2.1 g.) were heated together on a water-bath. Soon after shining crystals began to separate. The liquid was cooled after half an hour and filtered. The compound dissolves sparingly in alcohol and in acetone and crystallises from toluene in beautiful shining golden yellow plates, m.p. 199°, yield 2.8 g. (Found: N, 17.58. $C_{12}H_7O_2N_4Br$ requires N, 17.55 per cent).

Derivatives from other compounds containing a labile chlorine atom can be obtained in the manner described above and they are briefly described.

Derivatives from 1-Chloro-4-iodo-2:6-dinitrobenzene.

4-Iodo-2:6-dinitroaniline dissolves slightly in alcohol, easily in acetone, acetic acid and toluene. It crystallises from alcohol in orange silky needles, m.p. 175°. (Found: N, 13.42. $C_6H_4O_4N_2I$ requires N, 13.60 per cent).

4-Iodo-2:6-dinitrodimetnylaniline dissolves easily in common organic solvents and crystallises from alcohol in orange silky needles, m. p. 100°. (Found: N, 12.27. $C_8H_8O_4N_2I$ requires N, 12.47 per cent).

4-Iodo-2:6-dinitrodiphenylamine dissolves easily in common organic solvents and crystallises from alcohol in dark red plates, m. p. 135°. (Found: N, 10.85. $C_{12}H_8O_4N_2I$ requires N, 10.92 per cent).

4-Iodo-2:6-dinitrophenylpiperidine dissolves sparingly in alcohol and easily in acetone and crystallises from a mixture of alcohol and

acetone in yellow crystals, m.p. 99°. (Found: N, 11.17. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4N_3I$ requires N, 11.15 per cent).

3-Iodo-5-nitrophenoazine dissolves very sparingly in alcohol and acetone and benzene. It crystallises from acetic acid in violet silky needles, m. p. 210°. (Found: N, 7.8. $C_{12}H_7O_3N_2I$ requires N, 7.91 per cent).

2-Phenyl-5-iodo-7-nitropseudoaziminobenzene dissolves easily in alcohol and toluene and crystallises from toluene in yellow crystals, m. p. 209°. (Found: N, 15.06. $C_{12}H_7O_2N_4I$ requires N, 15.30 per cent).

Derivatives from 1-Chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrobenzene.

2-Bromo-4:6-dinitrophenylpiperidine dissolves easily in common organic solvents. It crystallises from alcohol and also from a mixture of acetone and water in shining golden plates, m. p. 127°. (Found: N, 12.54. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4N_3Br$ requires N, 12.73 per cent).

2-Phenyl-7-bromo-5-nitropseudoaziminobenzene dissolves very slightly in alcohol, slightly in acetone and more easily in toluene. It crystallises from toluene in shining colourless crystals, m. p. 174°. (Found: N, 17.78; Br, 25.23. $C_{12}H_7O_2N_4Br$ requires N, 17.55; Br, 25.08 per cent).

Some other derivatives of 1-chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrobenzene have already been described (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2481).

Derivatives from 1-Chloro-2-iodo-4:6-dinitrobenzene.

2-Iodo-4:6-dinitroaniline is sparingly soluble in alcohol and more in toluene and crystallises from toluene in yellow crystals, m.p. 158°. (Found: N, 13.35. $C_6H_4O_4N_3I$ requires N, 13.60 per cent).

2-Iodo-4:6-dinitrodiphenylamine dissolves easily in common organic solvents and crystallises from alcohol and acetic acid in orange crystals, m. p. 144°. (Found: N, 11.24. $C_{12}H_8O_4N_3I$ requires N, 10.92 per cent).

2-Iodo-4:6-dinitrodimethylaniline easily dissolves in common organic solvents and crystallises from alcohol in orange-yellow silky needles, m. p. 112°. (Found: N, 12.16. $C_8H_8O_4N_3I$ requires N, 12.47 per cent).

Diidotetranitrodiphenyl-p-phenylenediamine is very sparingly soluble in alcohol and acetone and crystallises from acetic acid as

dark red crystals, m. p. above 300°. (Found: N, 12.48. $C_{18}H_{10}O_8$, N_6I_2 requires N, 12.15 per cent).

2-Phenyl-7-iodo-5-nitropseudoaminobenzene dissolves sparingly in alcohol and acetone and more easily in toluene and crystallises from it in shining colourless plates, m. p. 192°. (Found: N, 15.05. $C_{12}H_7O_2N_4I$ requires N, 15.30 per cent).

3:5-Dinitrophenoxazine (m. p. 214°-15°) is identical with the compound obtained from picryl chloride and 1-chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrobenzene (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, 59, 722; 1924, 125, 2481).

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